

EXPLORING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GRADE 10 CAREER GUIDANCE MODULES IN KORONADAL CITY

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Abstract: This qualitative case study explored the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules to Grade 11 students of Saravia National High School in choosing their Senior High School tracks and strands. Homogeneous sampling was used in choosing the participants who were enrolled last school year 2020-2021 based on their tracks and strands. By utilizing a semi-structured interview guide to gather data, the responses of the participants were transcribed and analyzed by using thematic analysis. Results revealed significant themes in the participants' responses to different research questions. Regarding the participants' responses on how the Career Guidance 10 Modules changed their chosen career path, the following themes emerged such as alignment, interest, relatedness, decision-making, and others. Concerning their view on the effectiveness of the said guidance modules, the following themes emerged: realization, enhancement, cognition, and awareness, vitally important, well-guided, idea, essential, realization, understand, not difficult, readiness, trouble-free, alignment, not be wasted and effective. Since the findings in this study cannot be generalized due to having only fourteen participants at a single institution, future studies may be conducted in different settings to explore broader knowledge on the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules for further insights and help students in their career decision.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Grade 10 career guidance modules, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Choosing a career is a significant and challenging decision in the life of adolescents. They often feel overwhelmed by the various information they need to absorb when considering the numerous career paths they prospect to follow. Indeed, career decision-making is one of their bottlenecks. They are confused about what career they would take to match their skills, interest, and values.

Adolescence years are a critical period in life in which significant decisions are taken. Therefore, they are expected to gain a career identity during this period. They added that one of the primary developmental tasks in this period is career choice, and adolescents frequently ask what career will they choose to have a career identity. There is growing evidence that revealed that adolescents and even college students have difficulty in career decision-making (Kirdok & Harman, 2018; Marciniak et al., 2020; Rami et al., 2021).

Career decision-making is undoubtedly one of the most complex and challenging in students' lives. As students progress through college, they must be informed that career decisions remarkably impact their future career life. Unfortunately, for

some instances, changing courses could cause the wrong decision in choosing a career that could waste time, resources, and career frustration (Dangoy & Madrigal, 2020; Manapsal, 2018; Moneva & Malbas, 2019).

The start of the K-12 curriculum in the Philippines is also crucial and challenging in which students will decide the right tracks and strands in senior high school that match their skills, interest, and values. The educators and career guidance advocates believed that with the new curriculum trends, students must be guided in their career decision-making through the career guidance advocacy program because many students are confused and misguided. Indeed, the problem about the career decision-making of students and the need for career guidance is not only shown in foreign and national studies but also, it is accurate and observed in our local areas that many students were having difficulty choosing their career in senior high school.

With that, the Department of Education (DepEd) and the government have recognized the importance of a career guidance program, especially in selecting what specific tracks and strands to take up by the students when they enroll in Senior High School. Therefore, the implementation of senior high school career guidance programs is announced nationwide to assist the first old high school entrants in their chosen track, as stated in DepEd Order No. 41, s. 2015. There are a series of career activities. The highlights are the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules conducted to all Grade 10 pupils at public and private secondary schools.

The implementation of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules among the Grade 10 students started in September 2015. It was conducted to fully implement the Senior High School Program last school year 2016- 2017. As stated in the guidelines of DepEd Order No. 41, s. 2015, all secondary schools nationwide are required to conduct the said program to assist the Grade 10 students in choosing a career that suits their skills and interests and matches the community's existing resources.

It is also expected that all secondary schools, both public and private, will implement the conduct of the said activity. Furthermore, every school year, the researcher intends to evaluate the result of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules by exploring its effectiveness to Grade 11 students in choosing their senior high school tracks and strands.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules implementation is a continuous advocacy program of the Department of Education to guide the senior high school entrants in choosing which tracks and strands are suited to their career ambitions. Moreover, it has been four years since September 2015 that this Career Guidance Modules have been implemented; nevertheless, no assessment or evaluation would support the program's effectiveness regarding students' choice of track and strand.

This research study's primary objective is to explore the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in Koronadal City. Furthermore, it investigated the responses of Grade 11 students in Saravia National High School to assess whether the said Career Guidance Modules have a substantial effect on students regarding their chosen senior high school tracks and strands.

1.2 The Purpose Statement

This case study sought to explore the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules to Grade 11 students who are officially enrolled for the school year 2020-2021 in Saravia National High School. They were there during the actual conduct of the said Career Guidance Modules. Moreover, this case study would help the school administrators, guidance counselors, guidance advocates, teachers, parents, and learners to determine if the said Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules have effectively helped the participants in choosing their Senior High School tracks and strands.

1.3 The Research Questions

Specifically, this qualitative single case study sought to answer the grand tour question and the two stand-in research questions:

1. How do the participants describe the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in choosing the Senior High School track and strand?
 - 1.1 How do the Career Guidance 10 Modules change the chosen career path of the participants?
 - 1.2 How do the participants describe the effectiveness of the Career Guidance 10 Modules?

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Qualitative Methodology Design

This study used a qualitative approach. The qualitative method entails an investigation that seeks answers to a question and collects data and un predetermined evidence. Moreover, this method will help interpret the result and better understand the study's complex reality. Qualitative research involves an interpretative approach to its subject matter and a multimethod in focus. In qualitative research, the researchers study things or phenomena in their natural environment, trying to interpret something or phenomena in terms of the meanings attached to them by the people.

Moreover, qualitative research involves the use and collection of various empirical materials. It describes the everyday and challenging moments and definitions in an individual's life (Aspers & Corte, 2019; Boru, 2018; Busetto et al., 2020). This exploration employs the Case Study design. A case study is a qualitative approach in which the investigator explores a real-life, contemporary bounded system (a case). The multiple fixed systems are through the detailed, in-depth gathering of data involving varied sources of information such as observations, interviews, audio-visual material, and documents; then report a case description and case themes. Thus, it involves a thorough exploration of various viewpoints of the complexity and distinctiveness of a particular project, institution, program, or system in a real-life context (Creswell & Poth, 2018; Mohajan, 2018 Thomas, 2016; Tomaszewski et al., 2020).

This study allowed the researcher to explore the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in choosing the Senior High School tracks and strands of the Grade 11 students from the Senior High School of Saravia National High School. They were officially enrolled last school year 2019-2020.

2.2 Research Sites and Purposeful Sampling

This research was conducted at Senior High School - Saravia National High School, located at Purok Maharlika, Brgy. Saravia, City of Koronadal. The school promotes and gives quality education to every child. The Senior High School of Saravia National High School offers the following tracks and strands: Technical Vocational and Livelihood Education and Academic tracks. Under the Academic ways, the school provides the Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), and Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM). In Technical Vocational and Livelihood Education, the school offers Bread and Pastry Production (BPP), Agri Crop Production (ACP), and Computer System Servicing (CSS).

Homogeneous sampling was used in choosing the participants. It is the process of selecting a small homogeneous group of subjects or units for examination and analysis. It is also used when the research aims to understand and describe a particular group in depth (Elmusharaf, 2016; Etikan, 2016; Crossman, 2020). The fourteen (14) target participants underwent the actual conduct of the Career Guidance Modules.

2.3 Researcher's Role and Potential Ethical Issues

According to Creswell (2014), as a researcher, before conducting the study, examining and meeting the professional association standards and seeking approval from the institution and participants are vital and should be included in the study. Moreover, choose a site with no vested interest and negotiate authorship for publication. Further, it was emphasized that the researcher bears an obligation to respect the rights, needs, values, and desires of the informants. Thus, should be taken proper steps to adhere to such strict ethical guidelines to uphold the participants' privacy.

The partakers are considered an integral component of research studies. Therefore, there were guidelines proposed by Denzin and Lincoln (2011) to guarantee that the researchers will be virtuously considerate towards the participants in the study. The following are; (a) An Agreement or Informed Consent (participants after being advised about the nature of the study as well as its consequences must agree and participate voluntarily); (b) The Dodging of Deception (deliberate misinterpretation must be avoided); (c) Respect privacy, and confidentiality (the identities of the respective participants must be protected, as well as the location where the research will be conducted), and (d) Accuracy (gathered data must be freed from fraudulent, fabrications and the like).

The researcher sought permission from the office of the School Division Superintendent before conducting the research. He also asked for consent from the school principal before doing the same. He also notified the participants of the intention

and the proper process of the research study. Additionally, he asked for their approval. As cited by Wilding & Whiteford (2005), the completeness and accuracy of information from the participants must be comprehensive to be knowledgeable about the decision to take regarding their participation. Informed consent was attained when the participants compromised voluntarily in the study and signed the consent letter.

This study focused on exploring the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules among the Grade 11 students who underwent and personally experienced the said actual conduct of the modules. The researcher ensured the integrity and quality of this case study. He reviewed and met the professional association standard and sought approval from the school and participants' involvement in this case study.

The researcher must protect the participants through the application of appropriate ethical principles. Ethical considerations have a specific resound in a qualitative study due to the study process' in-depth nature (Steffen, 2016; Arifin, 2018; Kang & Hwang, 2021).

The researcher used a consent form before conducting the study. Inform consent involves a brief overview of the research goals, a statement about the voluntary nature of the research, the benefits and risks of the study. The list of the requirements for participation includes the consent of the participants and contact information for some questions and concerns. It is also a process in which the participants understand the purpose of research and its risks (Ravitch & Carl, 219; Manti & Licari, 2018; Xu et al., 2020; Hosely, 2021).

The researcher had observed anonymity in this case study. Anonymity occurs when the researcher does not know the identity of the participants when he was collecting the data. The participation of the participants must be voluntary; therefore, consent is necessary. However, there are situations or cases that the anonymity of data collection is allowed (Coffelt, 2017; Gordon, 2019; Collins, 2020).

Furthermore, the researcher had observed the authenticity of the gathered data in this exploration. The researcher ensured that the implications of the decisions in the study must be understood by the participants. The decision must be made in the context of understanding the benefits and potential harms that occurred from the survey. The participants should understand how their data would be used, stored, and analyzed, including any data relating to how they would be recognized. The researcher should consider the design implications, including how the data would be used in the future. Thus, the researcher should ensure that participants are informed of these details as part of the consent process.

2.4 Data Analysis and Procedure

The researcher systematically followed the process required for the analysis of data. In addition, asking for advice and consultation with my adviser was observed to gather the strategies or ideas needed for this study. In gathering the data, review, and evaluation with stand-in-questions were formulated with my research adviser's guidance and support to be directed objectively in interviews and discussions.

The individual interview was administered in gathering more honest and genuine responses from the perspective of the participants who underwent and personally experienced the conduct of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules, which were distributed by the Grade 10 advisers and the school's career guidance advocates in Saravia National High School. In conducting the interview, an open-ended questionnaire was applied.

Open-ended questions are used in qualitative research methods and exploratory studies, allowing the participants to respond in their own words. Qualitative studies that utilize open-ended questions allow the researchers to take a holistic and comprehensive look at the studied issues. Open-ended responses permit the respondents to provide more options and opinions, giving the data more diversity (Allen, 2017; Kabir, 2016; Wasil et al., 2020).

The data collection for this study started from September 2020 to October 2020. Before conducting the interviews with the identified participants, the researcher wrote a letter of permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of the Koronadal City Division and the Saravia National High School Principal. The consent forms were also sent to the participants.

The researcher conducted an orientation to the participants on the procedures of the interviews and discussion. He assured that all the data would be kept confidential, and they are free to express their ideas and opinions. Moreover, the participants

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were informed that the interview will be recorded through audio to understand and clarify the discussions. At the same time, all the key ideas will be noted and will be transcribed as the main conversations for review and confirmation of the participants.

In this case study, the researcher had used episodic records. Therefore, these notes were on the discussion process that would concentrate on the context to be observed. The researcher used the semi-structured approach in giving instructions to the participants. In addition, he supported the participants in describing their own experiences, including their thoughts and feelings.

Semi-structured interviews are non-standardized, and in qualitative research, this term is frequently employed. The interviewer has a list of topics and questions to cover, although they may not be covered in every interview. Depending on the route the discussion takes, the order of questions may also alter. Thus, additional questions may be asked, some are not anticipated at the start of the interview, as new issues. Responses will be documented by note-taking or possibly by recording the interview (Gray, 2019; Mueller, 2019; Busetto et al., 2020).

3. MAJOR FINDINGS

This qualitative case study research revealed significant themes with the participants' responses to different research questions. Regarding the participants' responses on how the Career Guidance Modules change their chosen career path, the following are the themes that emerged: alignment, interest, relatedness, decision-making, expression of self-and capability, success, utilization and preservation, creativity, absorbed and well-understood, personal preference, the right choice, understand and enlightenment. Regarding the participants' view on the effectiveness of the Grade 10 career guidance modules, the following themes have emerged: realization, enhancement, cognition and awareness, vitally important, well-guided, idea, essential, realization, understand, not tricky, readiness, trouble-free, alignment, not be wasted and effective.

Furthermore, the central theme was out of the textual data of the study. Therefore, the main themes are as follows: The Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules served as a catalyst, and The Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules effectively help choose the Senior High School track and strand.

Based on the participants' responses about what track and strand in Senior High School they enrolled in, the researcher found out that four of them (S1,2,4 & 5) chose STEM, six (S3, 10, 11, 12, 13, & 14) chose HUMMS, and four (S6, 7, 8, & 9) chose ABM. Thus, their chosen tracks and strands were aligned to their aspiration and desired dream careers. The researcher also found out that some participants chose their track and strand because it was their interest; others said it was related to their course when they pursued college. However, one of the participants decided to choose his second choice because the school did not offer his first choice. Also, one of the participants chose his track and strand because it was based on his capability and could enable him to express himself.

Regarding the implementation of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in their school, the participants described that the commission was excellent, well-organized, and delivered well. Therefore, it means that the performance was successful. Concerning how the materials were utilized for the activities during the conduct of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules, some of the participants revealed that they utilized the materials for the exercises given and preserved the output for future references. Also, some of the participants used the materials in making artistic things.

When the participants were asked how their adviser discuss the contents and objectives of the modules, they revealed that the contents and objectives of the modules were precisely translated into Ilonggo or Tagalog. That is why the contents and objectives were well-understood and absorbed by the participants. About the things learned from implementing the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules, some participants mentioned that choosing the track and strand in Senior High School must be your personal preference. Other participants said that good decision-making is also necessary. Moreover, some of the participants revealed that it must be the right choice. Furthermore, other participants noted that it must be related to yourself, and your capability.

Regarding how this learning helped them as a student who had been planning to enroll in senior high school, I found out that this learning helps the participants in decision-making as to taking the right track and strand fitted to their capability, interest, and personality. Also, it helps one of the participants understand the content of the way and strand she took. How the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules changed the chosen career path of the participants, I found out that the modules enlightened the participants in selecting the right track and strand in senior high school. It also helps in making a good decision, as mentioned by one of the participants.

Moreover, it also helps them discover their skills, values, and interests. I found out that the activities administered in the Career Guidance Modules helped them realize their talents, ideas, and interests. In response to how the participants' decision-making skills were affected by the Career Guidance Modules, they found out that their decision-making skills were enhanced in choosing the right track and strand in senior high school.

Regarding how their knowledge about Senior High School programs is affected by the Career Guidance Modules, the participants revealed that the modules affected their ability. Thus, they all became knowledgeable and aware of senior high school programs. The participants were asked how important are the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in choosing a Senior High School track and strand. They revealed that the modules have been vitally important to them in choosing their right career path; thus, they were guided in choosing the right Senior High School track and strand.

Regarding how vital are the modules to their parents, some participants said that they gave their parents an idea about their children's future. One of the participants (S4) mentioned that it was essential to their parents. Also, one of the participants (S6) said that they realize that choosing the track must be on the child's preference. Furthermore, another participant (S8) said that it helped the parents understand that their children's career choices should match them. Moreover, some of the participants told that the modules helped the parents in choosing the career for their children easily.

When asked about the advantages of choosing the right Senior High School track and strand using the Career Guidance Modules, some participants said they were ready to enter college. According to some of them, choosing the right track and strand would result in trouble-free making choices. Moreover, other participants said that through the modules, they could choose the right track and strand that are aligned with their skills. Furthermore, one of the participants said that he wouldn't waste his time and money if he chose the right career.

Finally, they were asked about the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in choosing their Senior High School track and strand. The participants revealed that the Modules have effectively helped them in their choice. However, one of the participants (S13) mentioned that the modules were eighty percent effective in selecting the Senior High School tracks and strands.

3.1 IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

This study was about the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules at a single institution. The following are some of the implications:

Since the findings in this study regarding the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules cannot be generalized due to having only fourteen participants at a single institution, future studies may be conducted in different settings. The findings of this study may be used as a readily available reference for any interested parties who desire to investigate and explore the people's perspectives and experiences regarding the effect of career guidance. Furthermore, the methodology used in the study will serve as a basis for student researchers who are interested in doing qualitative research in the future. Future research in different schools may be conducted to explore broader knowledge on the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules for further insights and help students make career decisions.

3.2 OVERALL SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This qualitative case study research would greatly help the school administrators, teachers, parents, students, and guidance advocates to better understand students' experiences in the conduct of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules and its effect in choosing the senior high school tracks and strands. In addition, this study will also benefit students and parents in increasing their awareness of the impact of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in choosing the senior high school tracks and strand. Moreover, this study would help the school administrators. It could be one of their bases in implementing career guidance activities to help students decide their old high school tracks and strands. Thus, this study can help guidance counselors and guidance advocates with their career guidance approaches. It would help them make the Career Guidance Program effective in guiding students to their career decisions.

Furthermore, this study would help other researchers get valuable insights and a basis for their future related researchers. Finally, I hope this research will shed light on the researcher in understanding the effectiveness of the Grade 10 Career Guidance Modules in deciding what tracks and strands to choose.

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